

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management—inorganic sources

Effect of P fertilizer on sulfur loss in flooded soil

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A lysimeter experiment was conducted on silt loam soil of a noncalcareous dark grey floodplain (Haplaquept) to investigate the effect of phosphate fertilizer on soil S loss and S balance in rice.

Soil had pH 6.6, 1.06% organic C, 0.09% total N, 13 ppm available P, 12 ppm S, and 0.13 exchangeable K meq. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications/treatment during 1990 aus (May-Aug).

The test crop was BR2 (Mala). Eighty kg N/ha, 33 kg K/ha, 20 kg S/ha, and 5 kg Zn/ha were basally applied along with

three P rates (0, 26, and 52.8 kg P/ha).

Aus is the heavy rainfall period in Bangladesh. From 26 May to 23 Aug, 1,135.9 mm rain fell in Mymensingh.

Rainwater S content varied from 0.99 to 1.25 ppm. Irrigation water used in lysimeters to maintain water level at 5 cm above the root surface contained 0.50-0.75 ppm S.

Phosphate treatments appeared to have the dominant effect on S content in leachate, which ranged from 1.23 to 4.08 ppm, with a maximum S loss of 54.2 kg/ha occurring in the P₁₂₀ treatment (see table).

The P₆₀ treatment recorded both the highest rice plant S uptake (10.9 kg/ha) and the highest grain yield (4.2 t/ha).

A negative S balance for rice was generated using inputs and S losses to

Sulfur balance sheet for rice.

Item	P ₀	P ₆₀	P ₁₂₀
Yield (t/ha)			
Grain	3.6	4.2	3.5
Straw	4.8	5.2	4.6
S input (kg/ha)			
Fertilizer	20	20	20
Irrigation	15.7	15.7	15.7
Rain	12.5	12.5	12.5
S uptake (kg/ha)			
Grain	2.8	5.6	2.3
Straw	4.4	5.3	4.3
S loss (kg/ha)			
Leachate	41.6	45.3	54.2
S balance (kg/ha)	-0.6	-8.1	-12.6

draw a balance sheet (see table). Phosphate fertilizer increased the S loss from flooded soil, resulting in a higher negative S balance for rice. □

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Green manure (GM) management and its effect on lowland rice yield

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Daincha *Sesbania aculeata* is an important GM crop in the lowland rice ecosystem in Tamil Nadu. We compared the effect of incorporating GM grown in situ with that transported from elsewhere and incorporated. We also studied the possibility of planting rice immediately after GM incorporation.

The experimental field soil in Coimbatore wetlands was clay loam classified as Typic Haplustalf with a pH of 8.3. It was low in available N (148.5 kg/ha), medium in P (Bray P, 18.9 kg/ha), and high in K (ammonium acetate K, 595 kg/ha). A split-plot design was laid out and replicated three times during Nov

1990-Feb 1991. GM levels (no GM, GM grown in situ and incorporated, and GM transported and incorporated) and time allowed before planting were in the main

Effect of GM management on rice yield. Coimbatore, India, Nov 1990-Feb 1991.

Treatment	Period between GM incorporation and rice planting (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Straw yield (t/ha)			
		N level (kg/ha)			Mean	N level (kg/ha)			Mean
		0	50	100		0	50	100	
No GM	1	2.9	4.4	4.7	4.0	2.5	4.1	4.8	3.8
	7	3.7	4.4	5.1	4.4	3.6	4.5	5.2	4.4
	15	3.6	4.4	5.5	4.5	3.2	4.2	6.0	4.5
GM grown in situ	1	4.4	4.6	4.9	4.6	3.8	4.2	6.5	4.7
	7	4.4	4.9	5.4	4.9	4.1	5.2	5.9	5.1
	15	4.8	5.1	5.1	5.0	4.9	6.7	6.8	6.1
GM transported and incorporated	1	5.2	5.3	5.9	5.5	5.3	6.8	6.8	6.3
	7	4.6	5.5	5.9	5.3	3.6	4.4	6.2	4.8
	15	4.5	5.5	5.6	5.2	5.0	6.1	6.4	5.8
Mean		4.2	4.9	5.3	4.0	5.1	6.0		
	1	4.2	4.7	5.2	4.7	3.9	5.0	5.9	4.9
	7	4.2	4.9	5.5	4.9	3.8	4.7	5.8	4.9
	15	4.3	5.0	5.4	4.9	4.4	5.6	6.4	5.5
LSD (0.05)						LSD (0.05)			
GM		0.24				0.69			
Time interval		ns				ns			
N levels		0.27				0.37			
Interaction		ns				ns			

plots. N levels (0, 50, 100 kg/ha) were in the subplots.

Daincha seeds were sown on three different dates at 1-wk intervals to allow time after GM incorporation and before planting rice. Daincha was incorporated